

FROM DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM PROSPECTS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the priority areas of development of the educational process are identified based on the application of digital technologies in the higher education system of our republic, the analysis of their capabilities. Also in the field of education through the study, systematization and generalization of the existing practice in drawing scientifically based conclusions on the introduction of digital technologies in higher education not only in terms of its important place and in what form it is introduced suggestions are given.

INTRODUCTION

From the first years of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, attention was paid to the issue of reforming the education system at the level of state policy, and the main goal was to educate the young generation in conditions suitable for world standards, to develop into a mature person, to reveal their abilities and talents.

All citizens living in the country, including young children and pensioners, are forming the idea that all problems in society can be solved through digital technologies. In addition, the robotization of production and management processes, for example, in the banking sector, is also a question of competition between robots and workers. rising.

With the undoubted benefit of digital technologies, issues related to ethical, personal data protection, legal aspects of competition between robots and employees of organizations are increasingly being considered.

In this regard, as the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said, "To achieve development, it is necessary and necessary to acquire digital knowledge and modern

information technologies. This gives us the opportunity to take the shortest path to ascension. After all, information technologies are deeply penetrating all areas of the world today.

Of course, we know very well that the formation of the digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, a lot of money and labor resources. However, no matter how difficult it is, if we don't start it today, when will we?! Tomorrow will be too late" [1].

It is possible to widely introduce digital technologies in state and community management, social sphere, increase efficiency, in a word, dramatically improve people's lives. Digital economy is not only a type of activity, but also business, industrial facilities, quality education and services. The term "digital" refers to the active use of information technologies in all areas. If in the ordinary economy material goods are considered the main resource, in the digital economy it is information and data that can be processed and transmitted. After their analysis, a solution for proper management is developed.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

From the experience of using computer telecommunications in various fields of education, it can be seen that information technologies create a number of positive opportunities for us, including:

1) organization of various types of collaborative scientific research of professors-teachers, scientific staff and students (really creative research, independent practical activity, independent knowledge acquisition, practical creative activity and other types of cooperation with the help of various scientific and practical projects);

2) organizing and delivering quick expert advice to the general public studying at the scientific-methodological center;

3) organization of the network of distance education and training of pedagogical personnel reach;

4) quick information exchange;

5) to develop the skills of mutual exchange of ideas, the culture of communication and their opinions quickly and easily among the partners in education, regardless of whether it is a student, pupil, teacher, researcher. and teaching clear expression;

6) to develop the cultural and social skills and abilities of young people as a result of the exchange of ideas with comprehensive positive information of cultural, ethnic, humanitarian [3].

When using information technologies in the educational process, we should teach students not only to see and accept information on the screen, but also to participate creatively in this process. Connecting the world of hidden opportunities connected with the didactic features of education directly with computer telecommunications has modern and promising goals in this field of education.

As a didactic function, we understand the manifestation of the external properties of educational tools used for certain purposes in the educational process.

As research methods, the study, systematization and generalization of normative documents, existing practice were used to draw up conclusions related to the formation of a scientifically based approach to the introduction of digital technologies in higher education.

It should be noted that the "COVID-2019" pandemic has affected the education system as well as all other sectors, including kindergartens, schools and higher education institutions, all of which went on vacation early. According to UNESCO, 1.7 billion students around the world were deprived of traditional education due to the suspension of classes. The closure of universities in more than a hundred countries forced 90 percent of the world's students to stay at home.

As of March 3, 2020, UNESCO reported that 290.5 million pupils and students were out of school due to the temporary closure of educational institutions in 13 countries and urged them to switch to distance education.

According to data, only 60% of the countries that closed educational institutions due to the pandemic in the past period have switched to full digital education. Some international experts emphasize that it is impossible to completely switch to online education, that this process should be considered as a way out of a problematic situation, otherwise the quality of education will decrease, while others emphasize that a new era has begun for modern education. The intellectuals of some countries are promoting the issue of provision of distance education.

According to Internet sources, 95% of students in only about ten countries have a computer today. In Indonesia, 34 percent of young people have enough access to the Internet. In other countries, this indicator is much lower. At the same time, this indicator is not at a high level in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The reason for this is that the Internet infrastructure in remote areas is not well developed. And this, as some experts predict, will cause the quality of education to drop possible [2].

Well, here comes the question. Are we ready for digitization?

Being able to foresee the danger, to correctly assess its results and consequences, ensures the safe exit from the situation. After the spread of the pandemic in the world, the necessary measures were taken to ensure the continuity of the educational process in our country, as well as in the economy, healthcare, and service sectors. In particular, this year

On March 17, 2020, the President's decision "On measures for the widespread introduction of digital technologies in the city of Tashkent" was adopted, and in this decision, specific tasks for the digitization of all areas of education were defined.

From March 23 of this year, televised lessons for students began to be broadcast. In addition, several higher education institutions have launched virtual learning systems for students and students. For example, at the Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi, the "Organization and Management of the Educational Process" information system and the MOODLE distance learning platform were launched. On the official websites of other higher education institutions, distance learning platforms such as MOODLE, Platonus, Moodle LMS, SRS (Student Records System), MOOC, and Google Classroom, Ereader applications for mobile phones and tablets have been launched and online classes have begun. In addition, the software of the distance education platform "remote-education" was developed and implemented in a short period of time at the Tashkent Financial Institute.

Prestigious private educational centers in our country have also launched online education based on the needs of the times. This process itself marks the beginning of a new

stage in the education system of our country. The reason is that until now no educational center has been able to switch to such an arrangement.

It is not surprising that today's educational system is being absorbed by digital technologies, because many things that are offered in the information space today serve as a basis for serious analysis and pedagogical study. It is also important that in recent years, no research has been conducted on the basis of any state project or survey on the problems of "digitalization" of education, its impact on its formation [3]. At the same time, we can see the importance of the influence of the environment on the Internet system on the minds of young people in the reports of the government, modern mass media, pedagogical public discussions, researches of graduate students and researchers, as well as deputies.

It should be noted that before we were limited to the implementation of digital technologies in all spheres, i.e. industry, economy, banking and other spheres. Today, taking into account that the digital economy is rapidly developing, deputy heads of all areas of digital development are included in the position. Digitization activation all implemented in business structures. Today, digital technologies are "aggressive" in all areas, especially where economic benefits are found, and are supported at all levels[4].

The dynamics of the processes taking place in the economy require an active position of the educational community in the analysis and development of proposals for the development of higher education in the digital transformation of the economy.

What needs to be done to effectively use digital technologies in education while maintaining the quality of teaching? First of all, we must improve the Internet infrastructure in our country, increase the quality of services provided by mobile operators, and create conditions and privileges for the most vulnerable population, especially students and young people, to master the latest achievements of modern information and communication technologies.

Secondly, to expand the scope of use of digital technologies in the organization of the educational process and to develop information resources, teaching tools and distance learning technologies, to attract creative students to university digitization projects, and to comply with the normative and legal documents regulating the activities of higher education institutions. to make proposals to the competent bodies on making changes, to organize centers including structures equipped with high-efficiency digital devices, classrooms, laboratories, media studios, etc.

use in institutions.

Thirdly, to ensure the solid integration of modern information and communication technologies and educational technologies, in this regard, to create additional conditions for the continuous development of the professional skills of pedagogues.

Fourth, organizing and conducting courses for teacher training on topics such as the use of interactive presentation systems, the development of interactive and multimedia presentations in connection with the Internet for lectures and seminar classes.

Fifth, to implement the process of distance education at any time using real-time interactive presentation systems, video conference systems, virtual halls, electronic resources.

Sixth, the use of cloud technologies, virtual reality, augmented reality and the use of 3D printing in the development of didactic materials and experience designs, the use of digital didactics and digital learning models, projects for teachers and students, diploma theses, scientific research, etc. discuss

it is necessary to develop scientific websites for Only then, using digital technologies, we will be able to provide students and young people with knowledge at the level of today's demand without reducing the quality of education. Q because if the tablet becomes an element of education, children will start the learning process with great interest.

It is equivalent to combining classical education with play. As a result, the learning process improves, assimilation, the level of education and the efficiency of personnel training increase. An educated generation, professional personnel are the guarantee of the development of the society on a large scale.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, summarizing the use of information technology in the educational system, it is possible to emphasize that today's classrooms are very different from ten years ago, and classrooms are equipped with computers, iPads, tablets, smart boards and other equipped with various educational technologies. As in other parts of the world, a new screen generation of the digital generation - television, computer, tablet, phablet, smartphone and smartwatch - is emerging in Uzbekistan. As a result of having such a dense digital environment and constant interaction with it, the thinking and information processing processes of today's students are fundamentally different from the previous thinking and information processes. The digital generation cannot and should not be taught the way our parents learned. It is not possible to use blackboard and white chalk in teaching this generation.

Changing the blackboard to white and the chalk to a marker doesn't change anything, it's not the way to motivate today's students to learn and develop the skills to succeed in the job market.

It should also be noted that teachers retain the main role in the interactive learning process focused on the needs of students. The reputation of the teacher and the effectiveness of his activities depend not only on the level of knowledge in the course content and his pedagogical ability, but also on the level of the teacher's use of modern information and communication technologies in the collection, processing and teaching of specific educational material. will be liq. In other words, education in the digital age must be revised and the educational paradigm changed, because students no longer want to learn in the traditional way, and teachers should not continue to teach in such a traditional way, but new innovations in the classroom. should be able to use it.

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